

Data-Driven PMT Calibration of Large Liquid Detectors with Unsupervised Learning

arXiv:2512.17866, NuPhys 2026

January 8, 2026

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Introduction

SNO+ is a 780 t general purpose liquid scintillator detector

- ▶ Charged particles deposit energy and produce isotropic scintillation light
- ▶ Detected by around 9000 PMTs
- ▶ Energy reconstruction uses number of PMT hits
- ▶ 2nd most important quantity is PMT hit times
 - ▶ Position and time
 - ▶ Energy corrections
 - ▶ Classifiers
- ▶ Accurate timing is needed for good event reconstruction

Time Walk and Electronic Delays

Each PMT has a constant delay and time walk

- ▶ Front end electronics give PMTs different delays
- ▶ PMTs trigger on individual thresholds
- ▶ Time walk: larger pulses biases to earlier hit times
- ▶ Parametrize time walk by PMT charge

Standard calibration involves a deployed laserball source

- ▶ Requires dedicated calibration runs
- ▶ Resource intense
- ▶ Contamination risk

Time Residuals

Time residuals correct event position dependence of hit times to first order.
For hit i :

$$t_{\text{res}}^i = t_{\text{hit}}^i - t_{\text{time of flight}}^i - t_{\text{event}}$$

Find time residual distribution from MC

- ▶ Fit skew- t distribution to MC time residuals
- ▶ Use fit as likelihood loss function

Dataset used contains ~ 7 million background ^{210}Po α events

- ▶ Abundant and point like deposition
- ▶ Distributed throughout detector

Figure: MC ^{210}Po time residual distributions

PMT Timing Calibration

We want to fit a falling exponential time walk and delay c_i for PMT i and charge q :

$$\tau^i(q) = a_i e^{-q/b_i} + c_i$$
$$t_{\text{cal}}^i = t_{\text{uncal hit}}^i - \tau^i(q^i)$$

If position/time of α from ^{210}Po is known

- ▶ Calculate $t_{\text{res}}^i = t_{\text{uncal hit}}^i - \tau^i(q^i) - t_{\text{time of flight}}^i - t_{\text{event}}$
- ▶ Fit timing model against time residual likelihood

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^{210}Po are distributed throughout the detector

- ▶ Could reconstruct α position
- ▶ Reconstruction depends on PMT timing calibration

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Solution: Fit timing and position reconstruction simultaneously

- ▶ As timing model is calibrated, position reconstruction changes with it

ML Based Position/Time Reconstruction

Fitting position and time across 7 million events to t_{res} distribution is challenging

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- ▶ Alternative: use neural network to find event position + time

MC Validation

To validate method, use perfectly calibrated ^{210}Po MC

- ▶ Uncalibrate with known time walks and delays
- ▶ Perform procedure and recover time walk and delay calibrations
- ▶ Leads to 0.14 ns FWHM accuracy
- ▶ PMT Transit time spread ~ 1.5 ns

$$\sigma_{\text{robust}} = \text{IQR}/1.35$$

Electronic Delays from Data

Delays come from front end electronics

- ▶ PMT electronics are grouped in crates, cards and channels
- ▶ Can sort PMTs by crate/card/channel number and plot delays
- ▶ Calibrated delays show expected crate by crate structure

Data Driven Calibration Comparison

Radioactive ^{214}Bi to ^{214}Po events provide data driven comparison of timing calibrations

- ▶ Visible energy > 1 MeV
- ▶ ^{214}Po has short (164 μs) half-life
- ▶ Minimal displacement from ^{214}Bi
- ▶ Reconstructed displacement of ^{214}Bi to ^{214}Po (ΔR) dominated by position resolution
- ▶ Better calibrations \rightarrow smaller $\Delta R \equiv \|\vec{x}_{\text{Po}} - \vec{x}_{\text{Bi}}\|$

Figure: Uranium-238 decay chain

$^{214}\text{BiPo}$ ΔR Comparison

Small (~ 6 mm), but significant, improvement in position reconstruction resolution.

- ▶ $\sigma_{\Delta R}$ assumes $\vec{x}_{\text{Po}} - \vec{x}_{\text{Bi}}$ is an isotropic gaussian

Electronics Monitoring

Change in delays may indicate change in electronics

- ▶ Found temporary timing drop in crate 11
- ▶ Out dated lower level calibration identified as cause
- ▶ Other plots use updated lower level calibration

Summary

New method of calibration performs well

- ▶ Accuracy on MC data is 0.14 ns FWHM
- ▶ Reproduces crate/card/channel structure of delays
- ▶ Improves $^{214}\text{BiPo}$ ΔR distributions

This calibration has numerous advantages

- ▶ Can calibrate using regular physics runs
- ▶ Much less resource intensive
- ▶ Can calibrate on a \lesssim weekly basis
- ▶ Can monitor electronics

Method should be applicable to other large liquid scintillator detectors